

COUNTER Usage Metrics

National Computational Infrastructure - ARDC Project Report (v1.0)

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The National Computational Infrastructure (NCI) has completed an investigation into the implementation of standardised research data usage metrics as part of the ARDC-funded National Data Assets Project impact/outcome monitoring systems work package. The NCI THREDDS data service was used as a case study for the implementation of COUNTER RD usage statistics. To better support usage statistics reporting in future, a number of design principles and NCI development priorities were identified. In addition, the project assessed the ability of the COUNTER RD standard to capture the complexity of data usage via HPC facilities.

BACKGROUND

The ARDC-funded National Data Assets Project included an impact/outcome monitoring systems work package. At NCI, this work package was focused on a trial implementation of the first release of the [COUNTER Code of Practice for Research Data Usage Metrics](#) (COUNTER RD). This standard provides a mechanism for capturing, processing, recording and sharing research data usage. The key metrics are the number of “investigations” (i.e., access to the dataset metadata) and the number and volume of “requests” (i.e., data downloads or data views/access), recorded per month for each dataset. COUNTER RD has been implemented by a number of high-profile international data repositories, including Dryad, Figshare and DataOne.

With capacity for over 150 petabytes of data storage, NCI provides a range of different high-performance data, storage, and computing services. NCI [data services](#) include an Earth Systems Grid Federation (ESGF) node, THREDDS, GSKY, the Copernicus SARA Data Portal and various optical astronomy data services. NCI supports researchers’ compute and data-intensive workloads. In order to access High Performance Computing (HPC) and Australian Research Environment (ARE), end-users require an NCI account and computing allocation. Usage reporting has previously focused on tracking data providers’ storage limits and compute allocations for HPC end-users. The number of registered users is sometimes used as a proxy for the level of

demand for data within a project. End-users nominate project codes when setting up HPC requests, but the accuracy and utility of this information is limited.

CASE STUDY

ENVIRONMENT

NCI's THREDDS data service was selected for the COUNTER RD trial as it provides open access to a large amount of research data. The THREDDS server includes services to allow individual files to be selected, as well as more advanced services such as OpenDAP, NetCDF subsetting, OGC WCS and WMS. It is popular with end-users and accessible programmatically as well as via a web GUI.

IMPLEMENTATION

1. Obtain sample THREDDS web log files
2. Generate COUNTER CSV mock-up
3. Map log entries to COUNTER report elements
4. Install [COUNTER Processor](#) application
5. Configure COUNTER processor using sample THREDDS log
6. Generate sample COUNTER report for selected Geophysics 2030 datasets

OUTCOME

Sample COUNTER JSON output was generated for several sample Geophysics 2030 projects (see Appendix II).

DISCUSSION

The project highlighted some challenges associated with implementation of the COUNTER RD standard at NCI. A key finding was that a significant proportion of NCI data usage was not captured in the sample COUNTER report. It is not always necessary to download a NCI dataset to use it for research. Direct access to data on the Gadi supercomputer or for HPC applications is not represented in the web service logs and COUNTER RD reports (see Figure 1). If a user logs into Gadi on the command line or runs an HPC task, usage is not recorded in the logs. The percentage of direct data usage varies widely by project; in some instances it may account for up to 100% of data access. Therefore COUNTER RD statistics can only offer a limited representation of total utility of different NCI data collections.

Figure 1: Data flows for NCI data usage. A) the traditional data repository from which users download datasets to their local compute and perform analysis on it there. B) users use shared compute resources at NCI to directly read the archive copy to perform their analysis without the need to “download” a copy first.

While COUNTER RD “requests” can include full or partial access to a dataset, tracking HPC usage remains challenging. HPC compute allocations could potentially be used as a supplementary usage metric. NCI has existing internal systems for allocating and tracking supercomputer time accounting. Originally, an NCI Service Unit (SU) represented “one core-hour of execution time” utilised by an application running on a given system. Over time, as NCI’s systems became more heterogenous and increasingly specialised, the Service Unit has evolved to represent a more generalised description of computational work. Some information is captured internally in order to manage these HPC allocations. When mounting HPC jobs, NCI users are prompted to select the required NCI projects (and associated data). Theoretically, the Service Units consumed could be divided among the mounted projects to provide a proxy for HPC usage. However allocation information is only recorded per high-level project, even though a given job might only read a handful of small files within this collection. Capturing HPC usage at a more granular level is anticipated to be a significant challenge due to the high volume of activity on an HPC system. In practice, users have also been observed to mount every available project in their research domain on a ‘just-in-case’ basis. While it is the primary method for using datasets at NCI, capturing and reporting HPC usage of datasets in a format congruent with the COUNTER RD standard remains elusive and will require significant development work.

NCI’s trial COUNTER RD trial also raised other questions regarding implementation. COUNTER was originally designed to track usage of research outputs such as journal articles and ebooks from publisher websites. The main use case tracked is a human user clicking a link to view metadata about the output, then clicking a link to access the full-text (PDF, HTML etc.). The COUNTER RD standard does not clearly specify whether accessing data documentation

constitutes an “investigation” or a “request” or if it should be excluded from the analysis (e.g., end-user downloads a licence.txt or readme.txt file or a PDF data dictionary).

The complexity of NCI data services and data organisation means that COUNTER usage tracking is not straightforward. For example:

- The range, scale and complexity of NCI data services and end-user access points makes comprehensive usage tracking challenging. Usage occurs across multiple servers and systems; the quantity of data stored and accessed means that log files are a significant size.
- The data structure in THREDDS (and other data services) has a complex hierarchy and does not always correspond neatly to the structure in the NCI Data Catalogue. Catalogue records may link to zero, one or more THREDDS links. Conversely, some THREDDS directories may not be represented in the catalogue. Depending on the project, the number of levels in the file system hierarchy will vary. However reporting must be at the lowest level of organisation to avoid double-counting. Data may sometimes be moved between projects depending on factors such as the funding for storage.
- Some NCI datasets are routinely updated (e.g., data providers have scripts to automatically update the data daily etc.). These types of dynamic datasets are difficult to version and catalogue for usage tracking. In some instances, NCI data may be restructured or moved between different projects or file system directories. This may further complicate usage tracking.

The case study revealed a number of lessons that can be used to prioritise and design future NCI developments:

- Close alignment of the NCI Data Catalogue to the data file structure is a key requirement to facilitate usage tracking;
- DOIs/PURLs need to be recorded when accessing the data via different data services and end-user access points;
- All NCI Catalogue records must include key DataCite/COUNTER metadata elements (e.g., DOI; creators; year of publication; title etc.); and
- Data services web logs need to be captured and retained long-term to support ongoing tracking usage trends over time.

CONCLUSION

Standardised data usage statistics are a key development to support FAIR research data impact reporting. Quantitative metrics help support benchmarking and inform a range of stakeholders, including data providers, funding agencies and repository administrators.

The NCI trial revealed some challenges associated with implementation of the COUNTER RD standard. Focusing on recording usage via web service logs underreports NCI data usage since it excludes ARE and Gadi access. In addition, to fully implement COUNTER RD at NCI would require

extensive development work across multiple NCI production systems (including the NCI Data Catalogue and network accessible data services). It would also entail a major effort to harmonise/synchronise data structures, identifiers and publication processes across legacy datasets as well as new data deposits.

In order to support more comprehensive usage tracking in future, the NCI COUNTER RD trial has identified a number of priority areas for development.

APPENDICES

- I. Sample COUNTER Report (TSV)
- II. Sample Geophysics 2030 COUNTER Report (JSON)

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research/project was supported by the Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC) under the Geophysics 2030 project. The ARDC is funded by NCRIS.

